

SIMULATING A 6D COOLING CHANNEL IN BDSIM*

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Abstract

Muon colliders hold promise for high luminosity multi-TeV collisions. However, novel methods of muon production, acceleration, cooling, storage, and detection are required. Thus, a cooling demonstrator has been proposed to investigate 6D muon ionization cooling. The Muon Ionization Cooling Experiment demonstrated reduction of transverse emittance using ionization cooling. The demonstrator will extend this to also cool longitudinal emittance. It would also use bunched beams instead of single particles from a muon source. The 6D cooling lattice comprises successive cells which consist of: solenoids for tight focusing, dipoles to introduce dispersion in the beam, wedge-shaped absorbers for differential beam absorption, and RF cavities for reacceleration. In this paper, the simulation and further optimization of the rectilinear cooling channel is discussed. This analysis extends existing numerical studies using BDSIM, a Geant4-based accelerator framework built to simulate the transport and interaction of particles.

INTRODUCTION

Muon colliders present a significant advantage over traditional colliders due to their ability to facilitate high-energy collisions. One of the primary benefits of using muons instead of electrons is the drastic reduction in synchrotron radiation. Because synchrotron radiation scales inversely with the fourth power of the particle's mass, muons, being much heavier, emit only a billionth of the synchrotron radiation emitted by electrons under similar circumstances. However, muons have a mean lifetime of only about $2.2 \mu\text{s}$ at rest, which poses considerable challenges in accelerator design, requiring novel accelerator concepts to efficiently produce, accelerate, and collide them before they decay.

Since the use of proton drivers results in the production of muons as a tertiary beam, these muons inherently possess an extremely large beam emittance. Synchrotron radiation cooling is not feasible for muons due to their high mass, and other conventional cooling methods take too long relative to the muon's short lifetime. Consequently, a novel technique known as ionization cooling was developed and tested by the Muon Ionization Cooling Experiment (MICE) at Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL) [1]. This involves passing the muon beam through an absorber material that reduces the momentum of the beam in all directions. The MICE experiment showed a decrease in transverse emittance and served as a proof of principle of muon ionisation cooling. The next iteration involves a configuration to show 6D-Cooling.

6D Cooling Demonstrator

6D ionization cooling is achieved using emittance exchange, in which the momentum of the beam is reduced when passing through an absorber but is replenished in the longitudinal direction via an RF cavity. Unlike traditional radiation damping, ionization cooling does not reduce the longitudinal momentum spread, and is primarily effective in cooling the transverse phase space. To enhance this effect, a system is devised in which faster-moving particles traverse more of the absorber material than slower-moving particles. This is facilitated by the use of a wedge-shaped absorber. Initially, a dipole magnet is placed before the beam to introduce dispersion, creating a position-momentum dependence among the particles. The wedge absorber is positioned so that particles with higher momentum travel through a thicker section of the absorber compared to those with lower momentum. This configuration can result in reduction of both transverse and longitudinal emittance.

Figure 1: A schematic of the rectilinear cooling channel for the 6D muon cooling demonstrator. The facility would also include components for phase rotation upstream, and instrumentation upstream and downstream.

The implementation requires a tightly packed lattice of RF cavities, solenoids for tight focusing, dipoles for dispersion and the absorbers themselves (see Fig. 1). Upstream to the cooling section a series of RF cavity would provide phase rotation in order to introduce a bunch structure to the beam. Instrumentation would be required upstream and downstream to measure the actual emittance before and after.

BDSIM

The study outlined in [2] provides a detailed theoretical framework within the cooling demonstrator. Simulations for this study were conducted using ICOOL, a program based on GEANT3 specifically tailored for the ionization cooling of muons. It is proposed to conduct this revised study using the Beam Delivery Simulator (BDSIM) [3]. BDSIM is a general-purpose, C++ based accelerator framework built on GEANT4.

A critical issue when using GEANT4 or similar tracking codes in accelerator physics is that small errors can accumulate significantly over many elements and, depending on the

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Figure 2: A 3D rendering of the cooling lattice in BDSIM.

application, over many orbits. Preventing this accumulation is computationally challenging. To address this, BDSIM integrates traditional accelerator tracking codes with thick lens accelerator tracking routines, which manage the propagation of the beam through vacuum. Simultaneously, it employs GEANT4 integration techniques to simulate the passage of particles through materials, ensuring accurate modeling of beam-particle interactions and physical processes.

IMPLEMENTATION

A model of the cooling cell with cylindrical absorbers and without dipoles has been implemented in BDSIM. A 3D rendering of staged cooling cells is shown in Fig. 2.

Solenoid Model

One of the critical components of 6D cooling cells are the solenoids, which are essential for achieving tight beam focusing. This focusing is crucial as the beam passes through the absorber, as it enhances the effectiveness of the ionization cooling process. The magnetic fields of the solenoids are largely dominated by fringe effects. The analytical treatment of these fringe fields follows the methodology discussed in [4].

Within the simulation environment BDSIM, an equivalent "sheet" model has been implemented to approximate the magnetic field behaviour of the solenoid. The analytic model of the field map implemented by BDSIM is given in [5].

BDSIM models the solenoid sheet in the form of a field map, and uses numerical integrators of GEANT-4 to implement the tracking. This is particularly advantageous as this lattice is fringe field dominated.

The on-axis field is designed with a form like

$$B_z(z) = b_0 \sin \frac{2\pi z}{L} + b_1 \sin \frac{4\pi z}{L} \quad (1)$$

and the radius and length of the current sheet has been selected to yield a field that matches this profile.

As shown in Fig. 3, the on axis field generated through BDSIM shows good agreement with the analytical harmonic model.

RF Cavity

RF cavities are essential components within a cooling cell. These cavities reaccelerate the beam longitudinally to

Figure 3: The on-axis field map of BDSIM, showing good agreement with the analytic model.

compensate for energy losses incurred while passing through the absorber. This is for maintaining the energy balance and achieving effective ionization cooling.

For the 6D cooling demonstrator, an RF cavity is specifically designed to operate in the TM 010 mode. An RF bucket for a 200 MeV/c reference particle was simulated in the lattice and is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: The RF bucket of the lattice is shown above.

Beam Tracking

Finally, a beam was tracked through the model. The field configuration shown in Fig. 2 produces a cell β function that has minima at the absorbers (i.e. beginning and end of the cell). The simulated beams were matched to the optics of the cooling channel.

This sets the harmonics in Eq. (1) as $b_0 = 7$ T and $b_1 = 0.1$ T. Passing a low emittance beam through the lattice, using the *G4ClassicalRK4* integrator, the particles were passed through the lattice and tracked through samples across 3 cells in the middle of the demonstrator.

Figure 5: Top: Optical plot showing the transmission of the beam across 3 cells, with minima of β_T at the absorbers. Bottom: A plot of momentum across 3 cells: The beam loses momentum at the absorber which is replenished at the RF cavities.

The optics were calculated. The beta function of the particles through the solenoid field is shown in Fig. 5, with minima at the absorber locations.

Additionally, on adding RF cavities and absorbers, the beam showed good agreement with analytic expectations. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the beam loses momentum in the absorbers and gains it back as it passes through the RF cavities. The emittance of the beam as a function of z is plotted in Fig. 6, successfully showing transverse cooling.

Figure 6: The transverse emittance as a function of z .

CONCLUSION

A lattice to simulate a rectilinear cooling channel has been successfully implemented in BDSIM. The solenoid model has been successfully verified, and the beam behaves as expected when passed through the lattice, showing good agreement with analytic calculations. Transverse cooling has been successfully implemented. The next steps include the implementation of a suitable dipole model to show 6D cooling.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Bogomilov, R. Tsenov, *et al.*, “Demonstration of cooling by the Muon Ionization Cooling Experiment”, *Nature*, vol. 578, pp. 53–59, Feb. 2020. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-1958-9
- [2] D. Stratakis, R. B. Palmer, “Rectilinear six-dimensional ionization cooling channel for a muon collider: A theoretical and numerical study”, *Phys. Rev. Spec. Top. Accel. Beams*, vol. 18, p. 031003, Mar. 2015. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevSTAB.18.031003
- [3] L. J. Nevay, S. T. Boogert, *et al.*, “BDSIM: An accelerator tracking code with particle–matter interactions”, *Comput. Phys. Commun.*, vol. 252, p. 107200, Jul. 2020. doi: 10.1016/j.cpc.2020.107200
- [4] Cx. Wang, K. Kim, “Recursive solution for beam dynamics of periodic focusing channels”, *Phys. Rev. E*, vol. 63, p. 056502. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevE.63.056502
- [5] N. Derby, S. Olbert, “Cylindrical magnets and ideal solenoids”, *Am. J. Phys.*, vol. 78, no. 3 pp. 229–235, Mar. 2010. doi: 10.1119/1.3256157